

Music Teaching Of Preschool Education Major In Colleges And Universities In Hebei Province From The Perspective Of Orff Teaching Method

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Abstract

With the promotion of quality education and the liberalization of the two-child policy, preschool education plays an increasingly important role. There are new challenges to the reform of music teaching in preschool education in colleges and universities. The traditional teaching mode has been unable to effectively mobilize students' learning enthusiasm, which requires that music teaching in preschool education in colleges and universities draws on the advanced

This paper examines the effects of the Orff teaching method on students' interest in music and their understanding of music culture, and lays a solid foundation for their continued study of music and preschool education in the future. In this paper, we studied music teachers and students in 20 preschool education institutions in Hebei Province, and obtained and analyzed relevant data by distributing questionnaires to verify that the teaching objectives, teaching methods, and teaching contents of Orff teaching method had positive effects on students' interest in music learning, students' music learning performance and class music learning atmosphere, and also combined with music teaching cases of preschool education majors. We also found that the Orff teaching method has strong applicability in the music teaching of preschool education majors in Hebei Province, and the integration of Orff teaching method makes the music skills course more in line with the characteristics of preschool education majors, and can effectively improve the comprehensive music ability of preschool education majors in Hebei Province. The integration of Orff teaching method makes the music skills course more in line with the characteristics of preschool education students, and can effectively improve the comprehensive music ability of preschool education students in Hebei Province, so as to cultivate a group of excellent composite kindergarten education talents for society.

Introduction

The Orff teaching concept is more commonly applied in the current preschool music teaching work in China. This teaching philosophy was first spread to the world from Germany, and scholars around the world have conducted in-depth research on the Orff teaching philosophy and teaching system, achieving excellent academic results and a series of scientific achievements. In the Western world, Orff founded a professional association aimed at teaching a specific educational philosophy and comprehensively promoted the promotion of this teaching philosophy around the world. In the 1950s, the depth and breadth of the teaching method was strengthened, and the teaching method was fully disseminated and developed around the world. The Shanghai Conservatory of Music was the first stop for the introduction of Orff teaching method into China, and professional associations related to Orff teaching method were established in various provinces and cities in China, and various types of teaching trainings were conducted, and the influence increased rapidly, and the teaching concept was widely recognized by Chinese education circles and spread rapidly throughout the country.

Although the Orff teaching method has been deepened and developed in the music teaching of preschool education majors in Hebei province general colleges and universities, the actual teaching effectiveness is still unclear. I have compiled and summarized the relevant journals and master's theses on the application of Orff teaching method in the curriculum of colleges and universities by using websites such as Zhiwang and Duxiu.

Inspiration of Orff teaching method to local music education

Hazel Bach (1932-2010), in his book *The Theory and Practice of Orff Teaching*, gives us a very detailed account of the origins and development of the Orff method, as well as the principles and the educational uniqueness and strategic advantages that it possesses. Togo Goodkind (2002) focuses on the development through independent learning and creative experimentation. The teacher is inspired to use more perceptual

thinking to integrate heuristic paths and to teach students' cognition from a "fragmented creation" process to a "generalized and complete" state through precise knowledge and skills.

Qin Dexiang (1989) argues that the Orff system should be analyzed comprehensively from a global perspective, and that the concept of Orff music education as one of the unique original properties existing in music education should be constructed; Tan Xiuli (2004) suggests through her research that in order to precisely master and naturally apply the teaching method, one must have a comprehensive understanding and control of the "originality" in the educational philosophy. The study by Tan (2004) suggests that in order to accurately master and naturally apply this pedagogy, one must have a thorough understanding and control of the "originality" of the educational concept. In the study, educational reform should focus on students' interest cultivation, comprehensive teaching, educational philosophy and other dimensions to carry out in-depth research and analysis, and organic combination with this teaching method, from which to explore innovative educational concepts and methods; Zhang Leishuang (2006) conducted a comprehensive review and summary of the process of the development of Orff music education method in China's education field, around the current long-term stable development of this education system in China. In his study, Fan Xiaoxiao (2007) pointed out that the traditional music teaching in China is not effective in promoting the creative and independent spirit of students, and that a teaching concept should be found that has a positive effect on the physical and mental development of students. (2006) argues that the originality in Orff's music education approach has similarities and differences with traditional Chinese music education, and that by using Chinese indigenous music as the starting point for research, it can maximize the contribution to the continuous deepening of Chinese music education reform; Liu Dufang (2006) argues that Orff's music ideas have a great fit with Chinese curriculum reform ideas (curriculum ideas, curriculum content, curriculum methods, curriculum evaluation, etc.). Li Bingni (2005) launched a multidimensional analysis of this educational system and conducted an in-depth study and discussion of its core educational ideas; the Orff teaching method elaborated by Bo Yajie (2013) is of great practical importance to enhance the development of students majoring in university music courses, and has a great contribution to the improvement of students' comprehensive musical ability, personality qualities and other aspects, as well as to promote the inheritance of folk music; Wang Lixin (2012) focused on the optimization and improvement of Orff teaching method in the process of practice, emphasizing that teaching must be combined with the characteristics of Chinese music; Qiao Xin (2008) proposed more educational models and teaching methods focusing on the co-integration of multiple elements based on teaching experience, which, as a popular new educational concept nowadays, will still develop into a global music education field. The trend is still developing as a new educational concept in the global music education field.

Research related to Orff teaching method in preschool education majors in universities

Wang Huijuan (2005) focuses on the multi-dimensional research and analysis of Orff teaching method in the teaching of instrumental music in colleges and universities. She believes that the organic integration of various forms of music teaching methods and Orff teaching method can greatly enhance students' interest in music teaching, and at the same time this teaching method is also applicable to the teaching and development of other subjects; Wang Yishu (2007) carries out an in-depth study and analysis by integrating Orff teaching method in the study of piano teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities, and the inspiration and guidance role of this teaching method for piano teaching at different stages. In-depth research and analysis were conducted. The feasibility and effectiveness of this teaching method in preschool education majors in colleges and universities are explored and analyzed in different dimensions.

Luan (2009) conducted a multi-dimensional study and analysis on the operability of Orff teaching method in practical application, and believed that the current music teaching in higher education institutions should strengthen the combination with Orff education concept, so as to effectively enhance students' aesthetic and creative abilities in art courses, realize students' pursuit and love of music, and lay a good foundation for the future employment of preschool students. Jia Xiaoxing (2011) analyzed and researched the experimental class of Orff, analyzed and researched the concept of Orff education, and based on this, elaborated on the necessity of quality education in music teaching, and carried out multi-dimensional and deep research and analysis on the role of Orff teaching method in the actual teaching process; Zhang Qian (2013) discussed the role of Orff teaching method in the music teaching of preschool education in colleges and universities. The current situation of the implementation of the Orff teaching method in music teaching of preschool education majors, and believes that this method can effectively help preschool education majors develop a love for students, and also help students' practical ability in future student teaching; Xiao Yu (2014) adopts the Orff teaching method can effectively improve students' interest in learning, thus improving students' learning effect. The concept of Orff teaching method is more in line with the professional characteristics of student teachers and can actively and effectively mobilize students' interest in learning music, which has very realistic significance in music teaching; Chen Bo (2014) believes that Orff teaching method is a more advanced teaching method, and it is very feasible to integrate Orff teaching method in the college preschool education profession. On the basis of understanding the characteristics of preschool education profession, focusing on the cultivation of students' ability, it is very meaningful to introduce Orff's teaching method into the future work of early childhood education; Professor He

Qingli (2015) focuses on integrating Orff's teaching method into teaching in the teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities, according to the "1+3+4 mode" of comprehensive penetration of relevant courses, student-centered and future career-oriented teaching, insisting on the holistic and openness of teaching concepts, focusing on the step-by-step teaching guidance, guiding students to improvise, and focusing on the localization of teaching; Chen Haoting (2018) believes that introducing the Orff education concept into the classroom of preschool education majors in colleges and universities can improve preschool education students' understanding of students, provide a more comprehensive understanding of the comprehensive nature of talents needed for early childhood education, and effectively promote the professional development of student teachers.

The above research results are mainly the research on the application of Orff teaching method word in college preschool education majors, and then by sorting out and summarizing the more representative research results of integrating Orff teaching method in the music teaching of college preschool education majors: Wang Yiqin (2020) introduces Orff teaching method as a new music education concept and applies it to the teaching of college preschool education majors, so that they can express their emotions through Zhang Ting (2020) introduced the Orff teaching method as a new concept of music education and applied it to the teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities, so that they can express their joyful emotions through singing and playing, thus making it easier and more accurate for them to master the emotions expressed by music; Zhang Ting (2020) started from the teaching idea of Orff teaching method and proposed a suitable teaching method for preschool education majors' sight singing practice according to the actual situation of the current teaching of preschool education majors' sight singing and ear training, and at the same time, combined with the three methods of Orff teaching method: "voice", "movement" and "vocal". Lei Xingyue (2020) points out that it is feasible to use Orff's teaching method for music teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities, and it has positive significance to improve the overall teaching quality of preschool teachers. According to the specific conditions of students, a method that is compatible with the needs of the profession is explored to create a better teaching environment for preschool education majors in colleges and universities; Feng Yunyun (2021) Orff teaching method, as a more popular teaching method, is widely used in preschool education majors in colleges and universities with its unique characteristics, which effectively improves the teaching level in colleges and universities; Liu Shuang (2021) proposes Orff teaching method is applicable to the music teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities. The reasonable use of Orff teaching method effectively improves the vocal teaching level of preschool education majors in colleges and universities, and lays a solid foundation for the comprehensive singing level of preschool education students; Zu Lingshan (2021), starting from the characteristics of preschool education majors in colleges and universities, combined with the current teaching status problems, encourages the integration of the advanced concept of Orff teaching method into the teaching of preschool education majors, from emotional experience to stimulate interest (2022), from his own teaching practice, made a more comprehensive analysis of the characteristics of Orff teaching and pointed out the value and significance of the application of Orff teaching method in preschool education majors in colleges and universities, and the integration of Orff teaching method into college The integration of Orff teaching method into the music teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities promotes the teaching reform of schools on the one hand and the development of music education teaching in China towards diversification on the other hand; Ding Wuzhi (2022) suggests that the reasonable application of Orff teaching method in the teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities enables students to successfully complete the learning of music in a relaxed and pleasant environment and improves the accumulation of music knowledge and basic quality of students; Hao Xingyue (2022) points out that Orff teaching method (2022) pointed out that the application of Orff teaching method in music teaching of preschool education majors in colleges and universities is of great significance to cultivate the ability of student teachers. The teaching characteristics of Orff teaching method and its unique teaching ideas have good reference value for college teachers to conduct music teaching, and its comprehensive and improvisational learning methods can promote the continuous development of music education.

Evaluation of existing studies

By collecting the research results of the above-mentioned professional education experts, we can not only understand the essence of this teaching method refined by various scholars, but also the theoretical knowledge and practical skills involved in this educational concept, which has invariably promoted the development of China's music education career and provided very sufficient theoretical guidance for the research I am going to conduct next. Through the above review and sorting of the application of Orff teaching method in college preschool education majors, it can be seen that the diversified development of music teaching method in college preschool education majors has received close attention from music educators in recent years. Many educational scholars also recognize the positive effects of Orff teaching method in various disciplines in college preschool education majors. Although there are still some studies on the application of Orff teaching method in college preschool education majors, there are still many shortcomings in such studies. Combing through a large amount of literature related to it, we can see that:

- (a) Most of the studies are theoretical, but not deep enough in terms of breadth and depth.

The main content of the study is focused on the localization of Orff teaching method and the study of Orff teaching method in a particular discipline. Teaching practice is the core of educational activities, and if it stays mainly at the level of research on conceptual aspects and on literature, the conclusions are not innovative enough and not convincing enough.

(b) The research method is relatively homogeneous.

More scholars use theories from psychology and education as the reference basis, and mainly use comparative methods and literature methods to carry out research on Orff's music education system, lacking relational thinking and interdisciplinary integration of research perspectives. The data analysis in the questionnaire method is not in-depth enough, and the overall coverage of the conclusions drawn is not comprehensive enough. The empirical method is less used, and it would be more convincing to integrate the empirical method into the applied research.

Summarizing the research of related scholars not only provides research ideas and research directions for this paper, but also lays the theoretical foundation for this paper. On the basis of the previous research, this paper combines theory and practice in the subsequent research. This study adopts the empirical research method of combining questionnaires and actual teaching cases, from theory to practice, summarizing the practical experience and then returning to theory, forming a closed loop, the questionnaire from teachers and students for two-way statistics, so that the data obtained is more comprehensive, teaching practice is the core of educational activities, if it only stays on the level of research on the conceptual aspects and on the literature, the conclusions are not innovative enough and not persuasive enough. If we only stay on the conceptual aspect and the level of research on the literature, the conclusion is not innovative and persuasive enough. Therefore, the research on Orff teaching method should be conducted as a whole to achieve breakthrough research results. This combination of multiple research methods also compensates for the singularity of previous research methods. In the past, more scholars used psychological and pedagogical theories as the basis for their research, and mainly used comparative methods and documentary methods to carry out research on Orff's music education system, lacking relational thinking and interdisciplinary integration of research perspectives. The data analysis in the questionnaire method is not in-depth enough, and the overall coverage of the conclusions drawn is not comprehensive enough. The empirical method is less used, and this paper is more convincing by integrating the questionnaire and actual teaching cases into the study.

Through sorting out and summarizing the above research results, this study attempts to take the general colleges and universities in Hebei Province as the base and focus on the implementation status of music teaching in preschool education in general colleges and universities in Hebei Province. Based on observation and study, we analyze it with a problem-oriented approach and integrate it with the characteristics of preschool education to explore the effectiveness and feasibility of this teaching method in practice. At present, preschool education is to create high quality composite talents for China's socialist development, and most of the higher education institutions are still in the process of exploring. We hope to achieve the organic integration and seamless integration of Orff teaching method with other courses of preschool education in general colleges and universities in Hebei Province, to boldly innovate and actively explore in practical teaching, to fully integrate this educational concept with the teaching practice of preschool music majors, to realize the benign transformation of traditional music teaching to diversified music teaching, and to cultivate more excellent talents for society. Only by continuously optimizing and improving the educational philosophy and teaching methods, and making drastic reforms to the traditional teaching mode with its shortcomings, can we make the music education in general colleges and universities in Hebei Province develop better. I have been engaged in music teaching in the front line of preschool education in Hebei Province for more than 15 years, and I have studied the theoretical knowledge and teaching methods of this teaching method, and I have been learning and improving it in teaching practice. During this period, I became interested in the combination of this teaching method with the music teaching of preschool education majors in general colleges and universities. Through collecting a large amount of literature, I have come to realize that Orff teaching method is very helpful to improve the music teaching of preschool education majors in Hebei Province and to enhance the music teaching level. I hope to make full use of my existing knowledge and practical teaching experience to provide a valuable reference for future research in this field.

Multiple Intelligences Theory

Howard Gardner's research has shown that an individual's intelligence is the key to determining problem solving when it comes to problem solving. Based on this concept, Gardner (1983) argued that human intelligence can be divided into seven categories, and subsequent research has increased the seven categories to nine, of which musical intelligence is one of the major categories. Musical intelligence refers to the ability of human beings to be creative based on their sensitive perception of tones, melodies, and rhythms after mastering them. In his book "New Vision of Multiple Intelligences", he points out that although musical intelligence is not mentioned initially, its function and influence are not to be underestimated and can even be compared with other intelligences. Therefore, we can fully realize that the cultivation of musical intelligence and is very important to

the overall development of children. The Orff teaching method combines performing musical instruments, singing and dancing, and combines the above with the actual needs of the curriculum to create diversified contents. It is generally conducted in the form of games that allow students to gain knowledge through play and learning and the freedom to express their emotions and develop unique and creative teaching methods to improve overall music learning. According to the results of combing with the research related to multiple intelligence theory, which Shangju Luo , and Lu, Sweet (2020) proposed that, guided by the theory of multiple intelligences, human intelligence is manifested in various forms, and music is one of the essential forms. In the increasingly developing field of music education in preschool education, diversified music education has a positive effect on the cultivation of students' interests, emotional expression, and improvement of skills and creative abilities. Wang, Yingfeng (2020) argues that the theory of multiple intelligences (MI) plays a guiding role in music teachers' thinking about teaching. By drawing on the core elements of the multiple intelligences theory, the teaching methods, teaching objectives, teaching contents, and teaching evaluation are adjusted in the process of music teaching, hoping to stimulate students' enthusiasm for learning music through music teaching, encourage students' independent participation while guiding them to give full play to their strengths, and open up innovative thinking paths for students, thus promoting the level of music teaching. Hou Min (2016) argued that music intelligence is a very important element in the theory of multiple intelligences, which provides a scientific theoretical basis for the overall development of human body and mind. In music teaching, it is important to develop students' multiple abilities, such as music perception, language expression, cooperation, and creativity, which are in line with the theoretical view of multiple intelligences.

Constructivist learning theory

The claim that knowledge is not the most objective presentation of reality has been promoted by constructivism. In terms of human understanding of the world, knowledge is a self-interpretation and assumption of reality, and therefore tends to change gradually with the increase of human cognitive ability and degree. When we encounter a problem that needs to be solved, we need to process and apply knowledge according to time and place. Moreover, although knowledge is recognized by most people through the external expression of language, this does not mean that all learning subjects have the same knowledge and understanding of the same knowledge. There are other factors that influence the overall knowledge and understanding, such as the amount of knowledge stored in the individual and the learning environment in which the individual is living. From the perspective of different individuals, the trilogy of learning is self-examination, self-improvement and self-construction, and students finally complete the construction of the knowledge system by actively constructing the knowledge structure. At the same time, students effectively filter and summarize relevant information in accordance with the learning environment. They then interpret the available information and develop their own personal understanding.

The knowledge base stored in each person's mind is different, and the points of knowledge that can be used flexibly are different, so the information obtained will be in different ways, and the results will naturally be different. The originality of Orff's approach permeates all aspects of teaching practice, and true music should be a wonderful art that combines language, movement and melody. Creating an environment conducive to student learning and active participation is an important part of the Orff approach to fostering student creativity. Following the ideas of this system, learning music does not allow students to simply enjoy music as an audience, but to participate as participants, with learners actively participating in learning, giving full play to their imagination, and creating music on their own, synthesizing the information gained based on knowledge learning and experience accumulation. The information obtained is called improvisation. The starting point of originality music is improvisation. Different learners have different improvisations because different people interpret and access the acquired information in different ways. Therefore, in order to awaken the deepest and most authentic musical feelings in students' hearts as soon as possible, students' creativity must be freely reflected. Xiao Zhang (2021) argues that with constructivist theory as a guide, for changing the traditional music teaching model, through teaching case studies, three main aspects of teaching objectives, teaching content, and teaching process are practiced, so as to establish a new music teaching model that can enliven the classroom atmosphere and improve students' creative abilities. Xie Wantong (2021) argues that constructivist theory is a scientific theory that promotes students' learning knowledge, emphasizes the initiative of students' learning, constructs their own understanding on the cognition of their original knowledge, and advocates the importance of cooperation ability in the process of teaching design, so that students can learn from each other and improve their own communication ability at the same time.

Humanistic Theory

Humanism suggests that the human psyche should be analyzed and studied as a whole, not as fragmented parts, but as an individual. The study includes dignity, beliefs, life, etc., which are psychological activities that are studied to a more profound degree. Humanistic theory is oriented to the whole person, including the whole process of learning and growth, and is aimed at developing human nature. It focuses on stimulating students' creative abilities by guiding them to actively build their knowledge systems and learning methods, leading them in teaching, and supporting them to realize their own self-worth based on their own cognition and knowledge.

Researchers focus on how to maximize the learning atmosphere and environment for learners and guide them to perceive and interpret the world from their own perspective in order to realize their self-worth. The purpose of humanistic psychology research is to describe the person as a whole, and this research suggests that researchers should focus on the uniqueness of the person and not ignore the overall self-perceived attitudes and "emotional values" that best reflect the person's identity. Psychologists suggest that to understand a person, one must learn to think and see things from the perspective of others in order to make changes in one's behavior. Humanistic scholars point out that human intentions, emotions, perceptions and beliefs determine differences from others, so it is crucial to create a learning environment in which students are the core of the subject in educational practice. Orff scholars have said, "Humanism has influenced my compositions and my actions in education, and perhaps the era of the humanistic ideal in education is slowly coming to an end, and perhaps the School Children's Music Textbook has been the last manifesto in this regard." Even though time has passed, it will remain in history. If humanism does come to an end, which I do not want and cannot believe, then too much of humanity in the West will have been lost and what is irrecoverable will have been lost." The underlying philosophy of the pedagogy is "humanism," the founding belief that "the root of music education is the education of the human being. This is the origin of all teaching methods, and it is the place where they should end." In inventing music pedagogy, he believed that music should be closely related to human nature, and that music education could effectively enhance students' ability to open their hearts and minds, to actively learn and understand music, and to achieve self-optimization. According to anthropologist Breggin, "people make music, whether they are musicians on the faculty of higher education or people living on the streets," and many educationalists have conducted research and studies around the purpose of education, believing that the cultivation of human nature is crucial in the process of education, and that it is by following "Humanism", according to the ever-expanding education system, which attaches importance to the comprehensive development of the individual and the emergence of the student as a teaching subject in the actual teaching process.

Mou Hua (2012) proposed that humanistic theory implements self-optimization based on respecting students' individuality. In the process of teaching, it is the students who are in the main position, and teachers play a guiding role, providing different guidance for students with different characteristics, and teaching professional knowledge while always paying attention to the changes in students' emotions. Chen Wen (2017) believes that the theory of humanism has some practical guidance for improving the comprehensive quality of human beings. It has a facilitating effect on one's aesthetic ability, moral cultivation, and creative thinking. Shi Ying (2017) believes that humanistic theory in teaching mainly advocates the student as the main body, is the relationship between teaching and learning that is emphasized. Respecting students' perfect personalities, the process of self-improvement is achieved through students' participation in teaching activities as the main body.

Conclusion

By sorting out the three major theories and comparing them with the characteristics of Orff teaching, the core contents of the three major theoretical foundations have a lot in common with the characteristics of Orff teaching method, which provides a scientific and effective theoretical basis for the design in the teaching case later. The teaching case takes changing the traditional teaching method as the starting point, incorporating the original, participatory and creative features of Orff teaching method into the new teaching method, encouraging students to build on their original knowledge reserves, the teacher takes guidance in the teaching activities, encouraging students to participate in teaching activities independently, and allowing students to learn from each other in the form of group cooperation through various forms of teaching, so that students can learn and grow in a relaxed and pleasant The classroom atmosphere allows students to learn and grow in a relaxed and enjoyable way, which not only enhances the effect of music teaching, but also strengthens students' music perception, creative ability and group collaboration ability.

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